

A Pre-Experimental Study To Assess The Effectiveness Of Video Assisted Teaching Programme (VATP) In Improving Skills on Antenatal Examination among Nursing Students in Selected Nursing Colleges, Jalandhar, Punjab, 2015

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Abstract : Good antenatal care links the woman and her family to the formal health system, increases the chance of using a skilled attendant at birth and contributes to good health through the life cycle. Inadequate care during this time breaks a important link in the continuum of care, and affects both women and infants. Keeping this in mind the researcher justified the need to assess the skills of nursing students in antenatal examination. An experimental research approach and pre-experimental static group design were used. The study finding showed that the mean post interventional skills score of nursing students in experimental group was 34.7 ± 10.13 and in control group was 19.33 ± 8.55 . This difference in the mean post interventional skills was statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ level. It was therefore concluded that after receiving VATP nursing students in experimental group had improved skills on antenatal examination compared to the control group.

Keyword:- Antenatal Examination, skills, students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is that wonderful time in a woman's life when she spends every day in joyful anticipation, waiting to hold her bundle of joy in her arms at the end of the ninth month. Every woman looks forward to a normal pregnancy and normal delivery so that she will be able to carry and raise a healthy baby. More than 95% of women have a normal pregnancy and delivery. These women require adequate prenatal care to ensure a normal physiological process.¹

Routine antenatal care is the best example of preventive health care. It aims to help and educate the mother in achieving optimum health so that the outcome of pregnancy and child birth is favorable for both mother and her child. From a cost benefit perspective antenatal care has been shown to be effective in reducing maternal mortality and morbidity as well as improving perinatal outcome.²

(University of Malta) The obstetric examination can be considered a special addition to the examination of the abdomen, its scope is to assess the characteristics of the pregnancy.²

The routine clinical examination of an antenatal mother includes general health observation, history taking, height, weight, assessment of hemoglobin, blood glucose levels, urine check up, abdominal examination and antenatal consultation.³

The obstetric exam is differ from other exams in that, the physician, is trying to assess the health of two individuals – the mother and the fetus – simultaneously. From the initial history, they should be able to judge the health of the pregnancy, any risk factors that need to be addressed, and any concerns from the parents. The history is an opportunity for the physician to find out how much the parents know about pregnancy, labour and delivery and if they have a preferences for which these events are carried out. A carefully taken history will also draw your attention to specific signs during the exam. Therefore, it is important that physician develop a concise and systematic way of taking the history and conducting the examination so that they do not miss any important information.⁴

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

An experimental research approach and pre-experimental static group design were used to study the effectiveness of VATP in improving skills on antenatal examination among nursing students. The Hypotheses (H_1) was formulated that : There was significant increase in the nursing student skills in relation to the antenatal examination after administration of the video assisted teaching programme at 0.001 level.

The study was conducted in selected nursing colleges, Mahatma Hans Raj DAV Institute of Nursing Jalandhar, Punjab & Lala Lajpat Rai Institute of Nursing Education. The study subject was chosen from the amongst GNM 3rd year students studying in selected nursing colleges of Jalandhar who have attended regular classes in prenatal examination. The study population was all nursing students from Jalandhar who have attended regular classes in antenatal examination. A total of 60 students were selected with purposive sampling technique i.e. 30 students of experimental group were taken from MHR DAV Institute of Nursing and 30 students of control group were taken from LLR Institute of Nursing Education. Data were collected after obtaining permission from the Principals of both Institutions and ethical clearance from ethics committee of

the institute. The study was conducted in three phases: Tool development, Intervention (VATP), and assessment of post interventional skills. The tool consists of three parts: Part –A Antenatal examination to obtain information on aspect such as Socio Demographic Variable age, residential area, religion, previous knowledge, exposure to antenatal examination and clinical experience for antenatal examination Part –B Observational checklist on antenatal examination. To assess the level of skills of nursing students on antenatal examination Part – C Video assisted teaching programme to assess nursing students skill level in the prenatal examination. Teaching was provided to the nursing students of the experimental group studying in the selected nursing college, Jalandhar.

Written consent was obtained from the student. The tool for data collection were: Self Structured Observational Checklist consisting of 50 steps. The tool was developed through a review of relevant literature and validate by experts from the field of nursing and department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology. After validation of tool pilot study was conducted in selected nursing colleges Jalandhar,

Punjab. Result of the pilot study indicated that study was feasible.

Thereafter a video assisted teaching programme on prenatal examination for 1 hour was given to 5 students in 1 hour to the students of experimental group and skill assessment was done on the 7th day. The post test of experimental group and control group was conducted at Civil Hospital & Chawla Maternity and Nursing home Jalandhar, Punjab. Observational checklist were used to evaluate improvement in skills in the antenatal examination among nursing students.

The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The analysis was performed with the help of the statistical package of the social sciences (SPSS-20) programme. The findings were explained and presented with the help of tables and graphs.

III. RESULT

The Video assisted teaching programme was effective in improving experimental group skills on antenatal examination.

N=60

Nursing Students						
Sr.No.	Group	Frequency (f)	Mean	SD	df	't'
1.	Experimental Group	30	34.7	10.13	58	6.35***
2.	Control Group	30	19.33	8.55		

Table 1: Comparison of post interventional skills on antenatal examination among nursing students in Experimental and Control Group

Maximum Score = 50

Minimum Score = 0

***Significant at p<0.001 level

This table shows the mean post interventional skills score on antenatal examination of experimental group was 34.7±10.13 and control group was 19.33±8.55. The difference between the mean scores in the experimental and control group was statistically significant at the p<0.001 level.

Hence it was inferred that after receiving video assisted teaching programme, there was improved post interventional skills on antenatal examination among nursing students in experimental group, so the research hypothesis (H₁) is accepted.

IV. DISCUSSION

The present study showed that 60% (18) students of experimental group were having good improved post interventional skills on antenatal examination and in control group shows that 13.33% (4) students were having good improved skills on antenatal examination. These findings are supported by a study conducted by Sarojini (2010) on compare the effectiveness between lecture cum demonstration with video teaching on antenatal examination among B.Sc. (N) students of a selected nursing college, Tamil Nadu.⁵

The finding of the present study also showed that there was significant difference between the post interventional skills on the antenatal examination between the nursing students in experimental and control group. These findings are supported by a study conducted by Scaria TM Valsaraj, Pias (2013) on video teaching over lecture cum demonstration prenatal examination were significant at the p<0.001 level significance level in improving nursing students knowledge and skills..⁶

Based on the findings of the present study it was concluded that Video assisted teaching programme (VATP) was effective in improving skills on antenatal examination as skills were measured by using observational checklist.

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